

Towards a Green Digital Twin for Life Cycle Analysis of Building's Renovation

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Abstract

This thesis presents a transformative approach to sustainable construction practices. It focuses on two core aspects: enhancing interoperability between Autodesk Revit and One Click LCA and implementing Dynamic Life Cycle Assessment (DLCA) analysis. In the interoperability domain, the study streamlines data exchange between design and LCA tools, significantly improving material recognition and automating processes. Standardized naming conventions and innovative tools like Dynamo scripts facilitate real-time links between Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and the model, ensuring up-to-date information. While some manual intervention remains necessary, the benefits in precision and efficiency are substantial. Furthermore, this work explores DLCA through a theoretical framework for the integration of Green Digital Twins. It provides a holistic view of building material impacts throughout their lifecycle, including indoor performance monitoring via RFID-based asset tracking and LoRa networks. The study also emphasizes the significance of standardized data collection for building components, ensuring data quality and enabling ongoing monitoring. Additionally, the thesis underscores the need to consider evolving energy sources in LCA studies. It demonstrates how accounting for potential shifts in the energy mix can impact LCA analysis results. This research culminates in applying these concepts to the

case study of Casa del Capitano, a rehabilitated historical building in Verona, illustrating the feasibility of implementing these innovative approaches in real-world scenarios.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/LYLT6pRwZWA>

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